

INVESTIGATING THE EFFECT OF USING PAIR AND GROUP WORK ON CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT - A CASE STUDY OF SOME SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN KHARTOUM, SUDAN

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Abstract:

This paper investigates the effect of using pair and group work on classroom management and improving secondary school students' performance in English Language at some schools in Khartoum locality. The objectives of this study are to analyze, identify and assess this method of teaching. The writer uses two questionnaires addressed to students at secondary schools in Khartoum locality (150 male and female students) and (50 teachers of English language). The data was statistically analyzed by the SPSS program. The findings of the study indicate that teachers agree that classroom activities help students to be active and disciplined. Furthermore, they hold positive attitude towards implementing group work which encourages students to participate effectively. The overall trend is that both students and teachers generally feel positive about pair and group work learning. The study provides some recommendations to tackle the problems of implementing this method. These are concerned with training teachers to implement this approach and to deal with the problems that may arise.

Keywords: classroom, group work, pair work, management

1. Introduction

This study investigates the effect of using group and pair work on classroom management and the students' performance. Through teaching and observing classes the researcher believes that classroom management and students' attentions are the most

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important elements of the learning process. According to Jones (2007: 2), *"a student-centered classroom is a place we think of the students' requirements as groups and individuals, and encourage them to participate in the learning process all the time. The teacher's role is more that of a facilitator than instructor; the students participate actively in the learning process. Both the teacher and the textbook are the essential elements which help the students and lead them in their learning. In a student-centered class, at different times, students may be working in different formations groups, pairs or individuals, every form suits a certain situation in the learning process"*.

There are different stages of conducting a lesson. Jones (2007:2) explains them as follow, *"First, students work alone, they prepare ideas or make notes before a discussion, and they do a listening task, a short-written assignment, or do grammar or vocabulary exercises. Then, students work together in pairs or groups. Finally, they work together in discussions or in role-plays, sharing ideas, opinions, and experiences which empower students' knowledge and broaden their minds. In the group work, students interact with the teacher and the whole class, ask questions or brainstorm ideas"*.

Jones (2007:3) concludes that the teacher will be helpful all the time while students are working together, to give advice, encouragement and facilitate things when necessary. By the end of the lesson and after students have finished working together, the teacher will give them feedback, offer suggestions and advice, make corrections, and answer questions. Students working together will result in, talking more, sharing ideas, learning from each other, involving, feeling more secure, using English in a meaningful, realistic way and enjoying using English to communicate with each other.

L.C.A. gives students the opportunity to gauge their learning. Therefore, learning becomes an incentive. Because learning can be seen as a form of personal growth, students are encouraged to utilize self-regulation practices in order to reflect on his or her work. For that reason, learning can also be constructive in the sense that the student is in full control of his or her learning. Such emphasis on learning has enabled students to take a self-directed alternative to learning. In the teacher-centered classroom, teachers are the primary source for knowledge. Therefore, the focus of learning is to gain information as it is proctored to the student. Also, rote learning or memorization of teacher notes or lectures was the norm a few decades ago. On the other hand, student-centered classrooms are now the norm where active learning is strongly encouraged. Students are now researching material pertinent to the success of their academia and knowledge production is seen as a standard because of their effective and vital roles both for teachers and learners as well as syllabus designers who are interested in educational process.

2. Objectives of the Study

This study aims:

- 1) To show the effect of using (LCA) on improving the performance of secondary school students in English language at secondary schools in Sudan.
- 2) To investigate the reasons behind using (LCA).
- 3) To find out the attitude of English teachers towards using (LCA) and how it can possibly affect students learning outcomes.

2.1 Statement of the Problem

Group is neglected by many teachers and they neglect its effect on improving secondary school students' performance in English language. Therefore, the researcher will take the problem to assess the effect of using group and pair work on improving secondary school students. From this point comes the main title of the study "Investigating the Effect of Using Group and Pair Work on Classroom Management". Using this method improves English language performance of students at secondary schools and universities in Sudan. As well as the students' benefits from the use of this method of teaching and its effect academically and socially.

2.2 Questions of the Study

This study addresses the following questions:

- 1) What is the effect of applying pair and group work on classroom management?
- 2) Why there should be group work instead of student-centered classroom?
- 3) What attitude do English language teachers, supervisors and school administrators hold about adopting group work in classes?
- 4) What are the problems that might hinder teachers from applying group and pair work?

2.3 Significance of the Study

The importance of this study stems from the fact that it investigates the attitudes of English language teachers towards the use of pair and group work in enhancing English language teaching. It also comes from investigating the effect of group work on classroom management. This research will be of great use to those who are involved in educational process.

It will benefit the teachers, as it suggests ideas which can help them to facilitate and enhance their teaching performance in classrooms and to provide some new ideas about modern teaching methods. It will help syllabus designers to think about the ideas to pick what is useful and design activities in their textbooks to suit this method of teaching. Moreover, language supervisors need to make some efforts and to follow up the application of the learner-centered approach inside the classroom. They have to remind and encourage teachers about the importance of this approach.

2.4 Classroom Management

Different people learn through different learning ways, and so do teachers, they teach their lessons through different approaches. Some classes have students with different learning abilities and interests. These kinds of classes spread all over the world. Therefore, a successful teacher should learn his/her students' abilities and background culture well. Some scientists want other people to believe in their own theories. They exert great efforts to experiment and get results. Then, they apply these theories and want others to try them, too.

Learning strategies are cognitive plans intended to facilitate the acquisition of the language. They were defined by (Nunan, 1991:168), as mental processes which learners employ to learn and use the target language. A learner then has to choose the way to accomplish his/her learning task. Here, obviously, appears the influence of the learner's cultural background, thinking style, personality, and educational experience. Kolb (1984:20) introduced his learning styles theory, which, is based on the Experimental Learning theory. His model is aimed at helping teachers and educators to identify and address the learning style of each learner within the classroom. The Experimental learning theory basically states that people grasp and transform knowledge through experience.

Kolb's model, in this regard, builds on the Experimental learning theory and identifies two main approaches for grasping knowledge: concrete experience and reflective conceptualization. Concrete experience according to Kolb is a way of grasping knowledge through action where individuals learn by active involvement rather than watching or reading. Reflective conceptualization, on the other hand, is another way of knowledge through watching and observing. To transform this knowledge, Kolb's model introduces two other approaches reflective observation (where learners draw upon what they have already learned including theories, textbook or observation of the others) and active experimentation (where learners transform knowledge by doing). Teachers have to spend time with learners on pre-writing phases, editing, redrafting and finally producing a finished version of their work. Although for learners this can be a laborious task, to avoid mistakes and produce a coherent piece of writing, it is better to adopt a process approach to practice writing skills. Each style of learning of Kolb's model requires a teacher to design his/her classroom method to address each learner's needs. For example, teamwork and discussion are the best ways through which a concrete experience learner can be involved. A reflective conceptualization learner learns better through observations and reporting briefly on what happened, whereas, a learner with a reflective observation style is good at giving theories and facts. Finally, an active experimentation learner can be involved through activities such as role plays.

There are three types of learners. The first type is auditory, those individuals who learn by listening such as reading aloud in order to hear and make sense of knowledge. For instance, a song can develop the students' listening, speaking and writing skills. The teacher could ask his/her students to listen attentively, and then write the words of the song, work in groups to check and probably correct mistakes. In doing

so, they are learning to repeat, words by heart, taking notes, re-writing, reading and re-reading, testing themselves and many more strategies. When the teacher succeeds in motivating the students to listen to songs and try to do the activities, they will try other songs in their free time. While listening to the song, the students are encouraged to take notes.

The next type is the visual learners, those who may learn through watching or looking at a printed material. Thus, when reading a passage, they can draw diagrams or maps to help in visualizing their learning task. The third one is the kinesthetic type of learners, those who learn better by doing. Therefore, when reading a passage, they may move around in order to process what they are reading.

The song as it was in the written form served the visual function, and on the tape, it served the audio function. Furthermore, when the students are asked to act it out by using facial expressions and gestures, it certainly served the kinetic function.

Brown (2007) provided his principles as followed:

- 1) Automaticity where learning is subject to subconscious processing. This cannot be clearer than it is in a song.
- 2) Meaningful learning takes place when the students hear, move, comprehend, repeat and sing the words. The students can retain the words longer than by just reading a text.
- 3) Anticipation of reward displays enthusiasm and gives the teacher satisfaction as it gives the students self-confidence and extra motivation.
- 4) The students will have strategic investment by developing personal investment of time and effort.
- 5) The students are given opportunities to continue their journey through the development of autonomy.
- 6) The role of the teacher is that of facilitator and guide who can plant the seeds of willingness to communicate with others.

According to (Nunan,1991), the learner in L2 should play an effective role in designing his/her own strategies without being burdened by the endless grammar rules that have many exceptions. They should feel free to acquire meaningful learning because this will help them retain the language they wanted to learn. The teacher must encourage the students to set their own goals for learning beyond the classroom. They should be able to assess their achievement and have their language skills developed.

A teacher can reach the heart of the students by encouraging them to role play, act, sing, tell jokes, laugh, solve puzzles, and play games....etc. Furthermore, a teacher should praise the students for making progress or trying out language in the class and out of the class with native speakers. Moreover, encouraging the students to state their weaknesses and strengths is very helpful in this regard. Thus, they will eventually build their self-confidence through team work which, can help the students learn more by competing and showing their commands of L2. If a teacher tape-records the students' voices, they will realize their mistakes in pronunciation, intonation and pitch compared with native speakers. They will gradually correct themselves.

When the students get a firm grip of the words of a song, they can express themselves more fluently because they can construct numerous sentences based on the pattern they have learned from that song. The patterns are easy to follow. When the applications go smoothly, the students will feel satisfied and gain more self-confidence. If the applications go wrong, they go back to the patterns.

In conclusion, a song can help the students retain vocabulary, grammatical patterns as well as having good enjoyable time. They can act out the words to entertain audience and gain satisfaction. It turned out to be more than successful with L2 learners. This is also applicable to teenagers and children. However, a teacher can use the eclectic approach to address the varied learning needs of the learners.

2.5 How to Address Various Learners

Mixed-ability classes are found in almost all educational organizations throughout the world. These classes accommodate students of different learning styles. Providing the same environment of learning for all those students in a class is a real challenge. To successfully face this challenge, teachers should take many considerations into account: the learners, the learning environment and the best way to plan and deliver instructions which meet their needs. Freeman (2000, p. 182) states, *“different methods are suitable for different teachers and learners in different contexts.”*

First, teachers should know what kind of learners they are dealing with. Using techniques like questionnaires or tests, they can easily determine their learners' strengths, weaknesses and their learning preferences. Other important things to know about the learners are their cultural backgrounds, personalities, ages and attitudes towards learning. Second, once the learners' styles have been identified, the teacher can design teaching aids accordingly and choose the approach which suits them. Moreover, teachers can put the learners in balanced groups when doing cooperative activities. In this way, they can provide the right atmosphere which makes learning occur. Strict pacing schedules and the limited class time are real obstacles in the way. To minimize the effects of this problem, some organizations include 'Review' classes, remedial classes (Remac) and self-directed learning classes (SDL) in their teaching schedules. Such classes make the pacing schedule more flexible so that teachers can spend more time with the learners and provide additional learning opportunities for them. Third, teachers should not stick to one teaching method as they have to address learners of diverse learning styles. Instead, they can select principles from each method and shape their own approach which works with the dominant learning style. Freeman (2000:182) states, *“Indeed, learners are very versatile and can learn well sometimes despite a given method rather than because of it.”*

For example, contemporary methods of teaching consider guessing words from the context as the best way of teaching vocabulary. However, not all the students have the ability to do so. Teachers, then, should prepare other ways to help struggling learners. Acting, showing pictures or tangible objects, displaying words on flashcards, dividing words into smaller components, and using words in sentences are other ways

of teaching vocabulary. Translating is another way of learning new words, but it should be the last resort. Brown (2007:436) states referring to translation, *“It rarely helps the students to internalize the word for later call or use.”* Some teachers prefer teaching grammar implicitly through the other skills of learning a language. This way, however, does not apply to all kinds of learners. Teachers may need to teach grammar explicitly from time to time. They need to explain rules and exceptions to meet the needs of slow learners. Another way of teaching grammar is having the students listen to a grammar item in a song, provided that it does not contradict with the learners’ culture. Harmer (2007:87) stated, *“Different cultures value different learning behaviors...When we espouse some of the techniques...we risk imposing a methodology on our students that is inimical to their culture.”* Games with cards sometimes work in teaching grammar, especially in matching columns or unscrambling words to form correct sentences. A balanced approach should, then, be taken into consideration to address all kinds of learners.

The time factor should be considered when teaching reading. While some students have the ability of ‘photographic’ reading, others have to read more than once before solving the related exercises. Teachers can, then, help the students do the pre-reading activities during the class and assign the reading as homework. To make sure the students do the reading assignment, teachers can ask them to make notes of what they read or summarize the reading passage. Harmer (2007:87) believes that oral reading is appreciated by some learners, but involving all students in such an activity is time consuming. Therefore, the teacher can be selective and chooses samples each time.

The researcher observes many classes and concludes that auditory learners achieve a lot in listening classes. They can hear a long aural activity only once and summarize the main points. Yet, teachers should not forget those who need to hear more than once. To set the scene, a pre-listening stage which includes oral, aural or visual activities is necessary. Moreover, the listening material can be played twice, and the students can be allowed to take notes while listening. When teaching speaking, teachers should take into consideration that although some learners can improvise a speech, others may need pre-task rehearsal. They may need to listen to a recorded topic or read a passage beforehand. Physical style learners can be asked to describe processes using tangible objects (e.g. the steps of making a cup of tea for oneself). They can present and demonstrate at the same time.

Writing teachers should not always deal with abstract concepts in their classes. It is too difficult for some students to write on abstract topics. Involving the other senses in the learning process may be of great help to them. Teachers can sometimes display pictures, photos or even real objects (realia) to be described. Also, they can tell stories and have the students repeat them but in writing. Students who like hands-on activities can be brought to the front, allowed to interview other colleagues (or the teacher) and write on the board. Most students benefit from cooperative activities. However, some of them are of the solitary learning style. Instead of participating in group and pair work, they like to work alone. For the sake of such learners, students can be allowed to spend time in SDL classes in labs equipped with computers. Teachers should assign tasks to

be done individually. In a quiet place with computers which have internet access, students are expected to learn better.

In conclusion, being knowledgeable about the principles of teaching methods and approaches is not enough. The question is how to properly put them into practice, and how to keep abreast of the new findings that pour in. Moreover, teachers should not cling to a particular method. Instead, a flexible approach which changes to suit the learners' needs and individual differences can be more effective.

Brown (2007:58) stated, *“By now, you may be able to ‘profess’ at least some of a personal approach to learning and teaching and have a beginning of an understanding of how that approach enlightens –or will enlighten your classroom practices.”*

2.6 Previous Related Studies

A study conducted by Abbas Suliman (2010) focused on exploring and identifying problems that obstruct implementation of the Learner-Centered Approach in Saudi Aramco English training programs. The researcher randomly selected 23 teachers (native and non-native) to respond to a designed questionnaire. The study distinguished certain problems which faced the implementation of LCA. For example, teachers were not involved when the decision was taken to adopt L.C.A. teaching and teachers, also, they needed enough time to prepare and design lessons that reflect L.C.A. strategies. As for the learners, the results suggested that they lack knowledge and skills as active learners and they also lack the intrinsic motivation to independent learning. Moreover, the study showed that the degree of LCA influence was affected by learners' cultural and educational background. In addition, a qualitative tool analysis was also used. Ten English language teachers were interviewed separately.

Vital results were drawn from these interviews and they were summarized into two main groups. The first group reflected problems related to the teaching materials and policies while the second discussed issues relevant to learners. Teachers believe that the use of very detailed pacing schedules and too standardized lesson plan form limit the teacher's freedom to select appropriate L.C.A. activities that suit their students. In addition, the interviewed teachers' think that there is too much focus on tests and exams and this does not help create a conducive/support learning environment.

Conclusions reached in this study showed that teachers are aware of the theory and trained in the practice of the learner-centered teaching of English language. However, they were not involved in the decision-making process of adopting LCA. Since teachers are an essential partner in this process, the training administration should consider involving teachers in the strategic decision-making process. As for learners, the study revealed that learners lack both understanding of their role and responsibilities as active learners and the intrinsic motivation towards learning. Regarding the cultural and educational background of learners, the study revealed some important issues that might hinder L.C.A. teaching. Teachers believe that learners' cultural and academic background forms obstacles against learning in general and to

the L.C.A. in particular. This indicates that more effort is needed to instill values of independent learning and permanent learning skills into Saudi Aramco trainees.

There are some similarities and differences between implementing L.C.A. in Saudi Aramco English training programs and in secondary school in Sudan. To begin with the similarities, both studies emphasize the great role which L.C.A. plays in improving students' performance. As for the differences, Saudi Aramco teachers are aware of the theory and have a great amount of training in the practice of the learner-centered teaching of English language. On the other hand, in Sudan the study suggests more training and awareness of implementing L.C.A. Regarding trainees in Saudi Aramco, the study shows that they lack understanding of their role and responsibility as active learners and the motivation towards learning. In contrast, the majority of the students in Sudan believe that group work is enjoyable, and it improves their academic and social life.

The second study was performed by Mamonaheng Amelia Matsau (2007), who researches the use of learner-centered approach in the teaching of English and Sesotho languages (the first language in Lesotho) in Lesotho (a country in South Africa) secondary schools. The research findings, based on learners' and teachers' questionnaires, observations and focus group discussions, indicate that certain learner-centered strategies suggested in the syllabus as well as other methods are used; and certain skills and content knowledge are acquired from each learner-centered strategy simultaneously.

The findings show that the learner-centered approach gives learners the opportunity to engage with those emerging issues that interest and challenge them, and which they must deal with throughout their lives. Learners are expected to be able to demonstrate a high level of social working relations and cooperation. Through working together in groups or in pairs they develop social skills which will assist in gaining knowledge in the classroom and later in life. One can conclude that the teacher training department has a challenge in ensuring that teachers are fully equipped with the variety of learner-centered teaching strategies so that they use them effectively and efficiently while teaching. The learner-centered approach produces learners that are fully engaged, learners that manage themselves and others, learners that use social skills, learners that think creatively to solve problems and learners that possess independent skills. As they do all these things, learners have to be aware and knowledgeable of their culture and other cultures. These qualities of learner-centeredness are reflected in the constitution and educational aims in Lesotho. All are aiming at developing and producing independent citizens who know how to relate with others under any circumstances. This brings a conclusion that teachers need to use the learner-centered approach as expected in order to achieve this. The education system also has to assist teachers in ensuring that most of the learning resources and facilities are in place so that teachers can do their job effectively.

This Study which was held in South Africa and the study that was conducted in Sudan have similar findings. Regarding students, both studies reveal the complete

engagement of students when they work in groups. Moreover, the study in both countries aims at developing and producing independent students who know how to deal with problems and become creative citizens. In addition, both researchers recommended that administrators and supervisors should assist teachers in implementing L.C.A..

Scientific research in the field of human sciences is a continuous series of continuous studies to complement each other and allow for subsequent research. In this part, the researcher deals with some previous studies that have been obtained and are related to the subject of the study, indicating differences between them and this study.

These include study conducted by Dr. Khayrazad Kari Jabbour (2013) from Lebanese university, in the study he explained that the typical Lebanese classroom is teacher centered, whereby the teacher is respected and is considered to be the bearer of all information. The title of the study is “Issues that Restrain Teachers from Adapting Student-centered Instruction in Lebanese School”. He states that student-centered teaching methods are not in the Lebanese teacher expectations and the usual teacher-student relationships in that learner are not expected to assume responsibility for their educational development by taking a center-stage role in their own learning process. H aims to highlight the issues that prevent teachers from adopting a student-centered teaching method. In his research study, the following research questions and hypothesis were addressed:

2.7 Guiding Research Question

What are the self-reported teachers’ perceptions on the factors that inhibit teachers from adopting a student-centered teaching approach?

2.8 Hypothesis

There is relationship between not adopting a student-centered teaching approach and:

- school facilities and resources;
- inadequate library resources;
- inadequate lab equipment;
- inadequate technology resources;
- class size;
- standard curriculum and standard tests;
- school leadership;
- staff professional development.

The instrument in this study was a paper survey that was used to gather data from 100 teachers from 10 schools ranging from middle to secondary schools selected from various areas in Lebanon. Participants completed a 10-minute surveys. The schools chosen for this study were located in urban areas with diverse populations, representing an array of ethnicities and socioeconomic levels. The teachers from all schools were treated as a single group; therefore, no distinction was made among the schools. This study was conducted in a manner that protected the confidentiality of the

participants. The instrument used in this study was a questionnaire administered in paper and pencil form. Survey items were developed based on an extensive literature review as well as querying participants using an exploratory questionnaire. The study gathered quantitative data to answer the research questions. The survey results were compared and tested in order to evaluate the reason for not adapting student centered instruction in the Lebanese schools. The survey results confirmed that lack of professional development training is a factor that inhibiting teachers from adopting a student-centered teaching approach.

The study concluded that the traditional Lebanese classroom is teacher centered; where learners are passive participants, with the teacher laying down the path of learning for them. This study described an investigation of factors that hinder teachers' opportunity to use learner-centered teaching approach. The findings from the study are: First, several of these factors are linked to School Facilities and Resources include lack of basic school facilities such as electricity, Labs, Library. Second, lack of school resources to support learning such as technology equipment including (computers, LCDs, internet....). Third, the overcrowded classrooms lead to high pupil to teacher ratio minimizes possibilities of individual attention to the pupils. Fourth, the heavy standard curriculum and schedule that the teacher should follow within short time in order to meet the standard examinations. Fifth, School policy and the unsupportive school principal. Finally: lack of staff professional development. Due to these issues, schools in Lebanon require the adaptation of traditional lecture approach of education, through which physical, human and financial resources can be controlled, also helps to control resources and on the other end requires limited human expertise and time. The researcher agrees with some points and disagrees with the others. For example, one of the study conclusions is that lack of staff professional development hinders applying student-centered reaching. The researcher agrees that it is important to train the staff and at the same time lack of training is not a reason to move to lecturing classes. As for the lack of school resources which support learning such as technology equipment including (computers, LCDs, internet....), the research believes that teachers can tackle this problem by using books and sheets contain activities suit group work. The study states that overcrowded classroom inhibits implementing LCA. On the contrary, the researcher thinks it helps teachers can break down their classrooms into smaller and easily managed groups.

3. Methodology

The aim of the study is to diagnose and analyze the problems of applying learner-centered approach at secondary schools. In this research, the researcher is trying to reveal the attitudes of students and teachers towards group work through a questionnaire. Teachers' questionnaire will be distributed to fifty secondary school teachers of English language, and teachers' interview will be distributed to ten expert

teachers. Students' questionnaire will be distributed to 151 students, who are learning English language at secondary schools in Khartoum locality.

In this research, the researcher uses the descriptive analytical method through applying questionnaire in order to describe the situation and analyze it from the point of view of the teachers and students. Eventually, recommendations based on the findings will be made.

Table 1: Teachers' Questionnaire

No.	Statements	Strongly agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	Classroom activities help students be attentive and disciplined					
2	The teacher needs to exert less effort in group work classes.					
3	Rotating group leaders encourages all students to participate effectively.					
4	Competition makes students enthusiastic for group work.					
5	Making groups requires longer time to prepare.					
6	In group work, it is easy to distribute roles.					
7	Working together helps students feel psychologically comfortable and secure.					
8	Group work always makes assessment realistic.					
9	Active learners dominate the task in group work.					
10	Working in groups doesn't affect class discipline.					
11	Group work allows teachers to monitor, move around the class and really listen to the language they are producing.					

Table 2: The frequency distribution of teachers' attitude towards the effect of applying group and pair work on improving Secondary School Students' Performance in English Language

Statement		Strongly Agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Total
Classroom activities help students be attentive and disciplined	Count	33	17	0	0	0	50
	Percentage	66.0%	34.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%
The teacher needs to exert less effort in group work classes.	Count	2	11	1	17	19	50
	Percentage	4.0%	22.0%	2.0%	34.0%	38.0%	100.0%
Rotating group leaders encourages all students to participate effectively.	Count	40	9	0	1	0	50
	Percentage	80.0%	18.0%	0.0%	2.0%	0.0%	100.0%
Competition makes students enthusiastic for group work.	Count	38	12	0	0	0	50
	Percentage	76.0%	24.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%
Making groups requires longer time to	Count	2	10	3	28	7	50

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prepare.	Percentage	4.0%	20.0%	6.0%	56.0%	14.0%	100.0%
In group work, it is easy to distribute roles.	Count	15	35	0	0	0	50
	Percentage	30.0%	70.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%
Working together helps students feel psychologically comfortable and secure.	Count	46	3	1	0	0	50
	Percentage	92.0%	6.0%	2.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%
Group work always makes assessment realistic.	Count	3	36	8	1	2	50
	Percentage	6.0%	72.0%	16.0%	2.0%	4.0%	100.0%
Active learners dominate the task in group work.	Count	2	4	5	6	33	50
	Percentage	4.0%	8.0%	10.0%	12.0%	66.0%	100.0%
Working in groups doesn't affect class discipline.	Count	16	27	1	3	3	50
	Percentage	32.0%	54.0%	2.0%	6.0%	6.0%	100.0%
Group work allows teachers to monitor, move around the class and really listen to the language they are producing.	Count	32	15	3	0	0	50
	Percentage	64.0%	30.0%	6.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%

Table 2 shows that, all (100%) of participants agree or strongly agree that classroom activities lead to a growth in self-awareness and in the understanding of others, good lessons preparation is an essential element in the learning process, competition makes students enthusiastic for group work, and in group work, it is easy to distribute roles, since the majority of participants agree or strongly agree that rotating group leaders encourages all students to participate effectively (98%), working together help students feel psychologically comfortable and secure (98%) and it doesn't affect class discipline (86%), and group work allows teachers to monitor, move around the class and really listen to the language they are producing (94%), while most of them disagree or strongly disagree that the teacher needs to exert less effort in group work classes (72%), making groups requires longer time to prepare (70%) or active learners dominate the task in group work (78%).

Table 3: Means, standard deviations and Chi-square test
 for of teachers' attitude towards the effect of applying group and pair work

Statement	Mean	S.D.	Decision	Chi-square test		Significance
				D.F.	P- value	
Classroom activities help students be attentive and disciplined	1.34	0.479	Strongly agree	1	0.024	Sig.
The teacher needs to exert less effort in group work classes.	3.80	1.278	Disagree	4	0.000	Sig.
Rotating group leaders encourages all students to participate effectively.	1.24	0.555	Strongly agree	2	0.000	Sig.
Competition makes students enthusiastic for group work.	1.24	0.431	Strongly agree	1	0.000	Sig.
Making groups requires longer time to prepare.	3.56	1.091	Disagree	4	0.000	Sig.

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In group work, it is easy to distribute roles.	1.70	0.463	Strongly agree	1	0.005	Sig.
Working together help students feel psychologically comfortable and secure.	1.10	0.364	Strongly agree	2	0.000	Sig.
Group work always makes assessment realistic.	2.26	0.777	Agree	4	0.000	Sig.
Active learners dominate the task in group work.	4.28	1.179	Disagree	4	0.000	Sig.
Working in groups doesn't affect class discipline.	2.00	1.069	Agree	4	0.000	Sig.
Group work allows teachers to monitor, move around the class and really listen to the language they are producing.	1.42	0.609	Strongly agree	2	0.000	Sig.

Notes from table (3) above the teachers strongly agree that classroom activities lead to a growth in self-awareness and in the understanding of others, rotating group leaders encourages all students to participate effectively, good lessons preparation is an essential element in the learning process, competition makes students enthusiastic for group work, and in group work, it is easy to distribute roles, it helps students feel psychologically comfortable and secure and allows teachers to monitor, move around the class and really listen to the language they are producing, while they agree that group work always makes assessment realistic and doesn't affect class discipline, whereas they disagree that teacher needs to exert less effort in group work classes, making groups requires longer time to prepare, and active learners dominate the task in group work.

All standard deviations (S.D) were about (1) which indicate the homogeneity of participants' attitudes towards all statements, the probability values (P-values) for all statements are less than 0.05, indicating statistical significance of the effect of applying group and pair work on improving Secondary School Students' Performance in English Language. The results of this study revealed that all of the teachers agreed that classroom activities lead to a growth in self-awareness and in the understanding of others. In addition to that, they agree that good lessons preparation is an essential element in the learning process. In contrast, 72% of the teachers disagree that they need to exert less effort in group work classes. It can be understood that almost all of the teachers agreed that rotating group leaders encourages all students to participate effectively. The results showed that competition makes students enthusiastic for group work. About 70% of the respondents disagreed that making groups requires longer time to prepare. The results also showed that 100 % of the respondents agreed that it is easy to distribute roles in group work. A great number of the respondents, about 98% agreed that working together helps students feel psychologically comfortable and secure, whereas 88% of the respondents disagreed that active learners dominate the task in group work. As for the teachers and their role in monitoring, moving around the class

and really listening to the language the students are producing, it was 98% of them who agreed.

Through the study, the researcher has come out with the following conclusions: the findings agree with literature review about working together when Watcyn-Jones (2002:9) states that the advantages of pair work are summarized in the points below:

- Pair work gives everyone a chance to speak in non-threatening environment.
- Pair-work activities are students-centered rather than teacher centered.
- The language produced during pair work is generally more natural and authentic than in teacher-led sessions.
- Pair work activities encourage co-operation between students since, in order to complete a task successfully, they have to work together and help create a very positive learning atmosphere in class
- Many pair work activities are a lot more fun to do than more traditional exercises.
- Pair work is dynamic and active. Learning cannot really take place unless the students are actively involved in the process.

Finally, P. W. Watcyn-Jones (2002:9) states that pair work gives teachers a break from being the center of attention, from having to 'perform', be dynamic, interesting, and so on. Instead, the teacher can stand back, listen more actively and think up strategies for helping the students increase their knowledge and confidence.

- It allows you to monitor, move around the class and really listen to the language they are producing.

4. Findings of the Study

This study tried to investigate the effect of using pair and group work on classroom management and improving secondary school students' performance in English Language at secondary schools and universities in Sudan

In investigating the problem of the research, the following questions were raised:

- 1) What is the effect of applying pair and group work on classroom management?
- 2) Why there should be group work instead of student-centered classroom?
- 3) What attitude do English language teachers, supervisors and school administrators hold about adopting group work in classes?
- 4) What are the problems that might hinder teachers from applying group and pair work?

In searching for answers to the above questions the following hypotheses have been made:

- a. Using pair and group work helps classroom management and improves the students' performance greatly.
- b. Group work contributes in developing the school environment, reinforcing the students' performance.

- c. English language teachers, headmasters and supervisors in Sudan do not hold positive attitudes towards group work.
- d. Big classes, lack of teachers' training and the type of curriculum might obstruct the implementation of group work

The above hypotheses have been verified in terms of the following findings:

- 1) Teachers agree that classroom activities lead to classroom management.
- 2) Teachers hold positive attitude towards rotating group leaders which encourages all students to participate effectively.
- 3) Teachers believe that competition makes students enthusiastic for group work.
- 4) Teachers agree that working together helps students feel psychologically comfortable and secure.
- 5) The overall trend is that both, students and teachers generally feel positive about student-centered learning. However, there are certain areas where more research is needed with respect to gauging students' attitudes about the social aspects of group work.

5. Recommendations

Based on the research conclusions, the researcher finds it important to recommend the following:

- 1) This study focused on some schools in Khartoum locality, further studies for future research could have more schools from Khartoum State to have a large number of subjects.
- 2) The study concerns secondary school students, further research should be concerned with students at primary schools, too.
- 3) Teachers have to encourage students to work in groups and pairs by making competitions between the groups.
- 4) Government of the Sudan should train teachers to implement this approach and to deal with the problems that may arise.

Problems are such as:

- How to deal with crowded classrooms in terms of keeping track of all the students.
- Having the students talk softly and still hearing one another.
- Being near from all the students to overhear them while walking around.
- Dealing with small classrooms by avoiding being part of the groups as students in small classes try to be teacher-dependent.
- How to deal with mixed-ability classes by changing the seating plan every now and then so that factors can share ideas. Moreover, when and how to switch from a method to another to meet different personalities, different ages, and different learning styles.

5.1 Suggestions for Further Studies

According to the research conclusions, researchers in the future should select a larger population and sample size in order to get accurate findings. Further studies on the same topic should explore more factors that could make the implementation of the L.C.A. an important issue so as to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of its effect on improving English Language performance at the secondary schools in Sudan. Moreover, researchers are required to conduct more studies on gauging students' attitudes about the social aspects of group work. For further studies, other factors which have not been covered in this study can be identified to see how they lead to the improvement of the students' performance.

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